

EVALUATION OF HIGH TEMPERATURE DEGRADATION IN COMPOSITES USING ACOUSTO-ULTRASONIC TECHNIQUES

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ABSTRACT

The paper proposes to use acousto-ultrasonics, a relatively new non-destructive technique, to detect degradation in composites due to overheating. Neat resin and unidirectional carbon/epoxy composite panels have been exposed to thermal cycling and evaluated using acousto-ultrasonic techniques and destructive mechanical testing. Advanced signal processing technologies and pattern recognition are suggested to decipher the acousto-ultrasonic signals according to the state of degradation of the material. Correlation between acousto-ultrasonic measurements and mechanical properties is made.

Keywords: polymeric composites, thermal degradation, acousto-ultrasonics, signal processing, pattern recognition.

1. INTRODUCTION

The use of polymeric based composites in aerospace applications often exposes these materials to extreme thermal spikes over relatively short time spans. Depending on the characteristics of the spike and the composition of the material, thermal spikes may lead to either matrix or fibre-matrix interface degradation resulting in a possible reduction in mechanical properties [1]. Overheating is often revealed by either the discolouration or blistering of paint but, without removing the component so that mechanical tests can be carried out, it is difficult to determine whether material beneath the composite surface has been damaged and, if so, to what extent the mechanical properties of the structure have been affected. There is obviously a need for a simple non-destructive inspection procedure that can detect degradation of composites and associated changes in mechanical properties resulting from overheating.

The majority of NDT techniques currently available for in-service inspection are only capable of detecting gross physical defects such as delamination and disbonds. On the other hand, overheating of composites may change either the morphology, microstructure, state of cure and porosity of the matrix or result in a myriad of microscopical defects which are not easily

detectable by conventional NDT methods. One technique that has shown potential in detecting a diffuse flaw population and associated changes in mechanical properties is acousto-ultrasonics (AU) [2-6].

In this study, in addition to the further exploration of the ability of the AU technique to detect thermal degradation in composites, advanced signal processing technologies were used to analyze and interpret the AU signals and classify them according to the state of degradation of the material.

2. BACKGROUND

2.1 Acousto-ultrasonic technique

In the acousto-ultrasonic technique repetitive pulses are transmitted into the test material by a large broadband transducer as shown in Figure 1. The resulting stress waves propagate in all

Figure 1. A schematic diagram of the AU system used in the present study

directions in the material. A receiving sensor is placed at a distance from the transmitting transducer on the same side of the specimen to intercept the propagating stress waves. In this way the efficiency of the material in transmitting stress waves is evaluated by analyzing the total received signal. Minute microstructural defects influence stress wave transmission efficiency which in turn affects the total received signal. The AU signals obtained from the technique are very rich in information making their interpretation complicated and rendering signal processing techniques necessary. In order to assess changes in properties such as strength, moduli and toughness from the AU signals, better advanced models of wave-

material interactions, better experimental equipment (transducers, acquisition system...) and more advanced signal processing techniques need to be developed. Advanced signal processing methods have been used elsewhere [7-9] to extract from acoustic emission signals detailed information on the type of damage developing in composites.

2.2 Signal Processing and Recognition Strategies

Digital signal processing is used to analyze digitized AU signals and extract from them several parameters. A parameter (also called a feature) describes one characteristic of a signal which may be related to time or frequency domains. All the features used in this study are listed in Table 1. Some of them taken from previous works on AU and acoustic emission analysis are detailed elsewhere [7,9]. Using a feature vector, built with the parameters the best able to classify the signals according to the state of degradation of the material, the AU database is classified by pattern recognition techniques. Pattern recognition is one way to decipher the complex multivariate data set generated by the signal processing analyses in order to obtain discriminatory information carried by the AU signals. This technique finds the natural division between classes of signals and in certain cases to identify the signal sources. In the present investigation,

Table 1. Features extracted from each AU signal

Features in time and frequency domain	
ME, MEF	Mean of the signal and the spectrum
DE, DEF	Standard deviation
M3, M3F	Skewness
M4, M4F	Kurtosis
C ₀ , C ₁ , C ₂ , C ₃	Crossing feature at 0, 1, 2, and 3 times DE
Features in time domain	
RI	Rise time
AM	Maximum amplitude
PK	Peak to peak
DE	Duration of the signal
EN	Energy
NPKN	Normalized numbers of peak
RMS	Root mean square
Features in frequency domain	
FF	Largest frequency peak
F _i	Maximum frequency in each part i of the spectrum
A _i	Areas of each part i of the spectrum
NA _i	A _i /total area
S _i	A _i /M _i * (F _{i+1} -F _i); M _i being the highest amplitude peak in the frequency band
RF _i	(F _i -f _i)/(F _{i+1} -f _i); relative position of the F _i in the ith frequency band

conventional pattern recognition technique based on statistical multivariate analysis (cluster analysis, linear discriminant analysis, k-means...) was extensively used. The classification of AU signals by this analysis involves the following steps:

- AU data reduction and partitioning of observations on a set of training patterns related to the state of thermal degradation
- the establishment of a decision rule based on a set of observations of known classes (training step)
- the application of the decision rule to identify and classify other observations whose states are unknown (testing step).

The decision rule used here is based on the linear discriminant function [7].

An other pattern recognition method, neural networks [9,10], which is a technique newly applied in ultrasonic evaluation was also explored. The method offers a potential alternative to the traditional classification techniques. It is especially useful for problems having lots of data available but to which mathematical relationships cannot be easily derived. The ability of learning, even from ambiguous or contradictory information, may be the most important advantage for using neural networks in AU signal processing. This ability bears a resemblance to the human brain in the sense that knowledge and experience are acquired through learning rather than programming.

3. EXPERIMENTAL AND ANALYTICAL PROCEDURE

An overview of the experimental and analytical procedures utilized in this study is shown in Figure 2.

1. For the composite only

Figure 2. Overview of the experimental and analytical procedure

3.1 Materials and Thermal Conditioning

A trifunctional, high temperature epoxy produced by Dow Chemical Company as DOW TACTIX 742 was used to produce non-reinforced resin panels of 140mm by 300mm. Unidirectional composite panels of the same size with 24 plies and a nominal fibre volume fraction of 60% were fabricated from carbon/epoxy AS4/3501-6 prepreg material; fibre direction was parallel to the 300mm side. Resin and composite panels were cured according to the manufacturer's recommended curing cycle which included in both cases two hours at 177°C.

For thermal exposure, panels were placed 25mm apart on an aluminum rack which was then inserted into a preheated programmable furnace. The temperature of the panels was monitored by a thermocouple placed on the center of the panels. Once the desired temperature was reached (around 12 minutes) the panels were removed from the furnace and allowed to cool to room temperature in a fume hood (around 25 minutes). Resin panels experienced 21 cycles in total (all to 235°C). This temperature was chosen because it is above the service temperature and was about the maximum temperature at which damage was not visually observed. After 0 (virgin), 5, 11, 16 and 21 thermal cycles, they were subjected to acousto-ultrasonic measurements and specimens which were cut from the panels were mechanically tested. The composite panels experienced a total of 40 cycles, 235°C for the first thirty cycles, 250°C the next five cycles and 255°C the last five cycles. After 0 (virgin), 10, 20, 30 and 40 thermal cycles, they were C-scanned, subjected to acousto-ultrasonic measurements and specimens cut from the panels were mechanically tested. For each thermal conditioning, either for the resin or the composite, three panels were used. The lower number of cycles of thermal exposure for the resin was chosen because of the higher rate of degradation observable with the unaided eye.

3.2 Acousto-ultrasonic Measurements

The acousto-ultrasonic measurements were carried out using the apparatus shown schematically in Figure 1. A pulse generator was used to produce the input signals which excited a broadband transmitting transducer (0.1-2.0 MHz frequency). At a fixed distance, a receiving transducer (0.1-1MHz frequency) was used to intercept the stress waves which were amplified and filtered using a 2 MHz bandpass filter, then digitized using a signal acquisition and processing system and stored on floppy disks for further analysis on a computer. The acquisition system had a sampling period set at 300ns which covered frequencies up to approximately 1.6 MHz. The completely digitized sampled signal contained 1024 points which were considered adequate to cover the entire AU response to an input pulse. A total of 10 measurements were taken on each panel. After each measurement, the transducers were removed, cleaned and then recoupled to the cleaned surface with newly applied coupling fluid. A jig was used to ensure that the transducers were relocated at the same position on the panel which corresponded to the center of the panel and that the distance between the transducers remained fixed. In the case of the composite, AU measurements were taken parallel as well as perpendicular to the fibres.

3.3 Processing Softwares

Software routines were developed to facilitate rapid transfer and ASCII code conversion of signals to PC microcomputer. Features extraction from the signals and signal classification were achieved employing pattern recognition routines adapted from the software Statistical Analysis System (SAS). The architecture of neural network used to classify the signal was developed in the Neural Works Explorer of Neuralware Inc. Neural computing was based on back-propagation algorithm.

3.4 Mechanical Testing and Microscopy

For the resin, two tensile specimens were cut from the centre of panels along the length and to the dimensions of ASTM D638-89. They were loaded in tension and the tensile strength was calculated. For the composite, five short beam shear specimens were cut from the centre of panels along the fibre direction to the dimensions according to ASTM D2344-84. They were loaded in a three-point loading fixture and the shear strength was calculated. The short beam shear test was chosen as it indicates the quality of the fibre/matrix interface of the composite which is expected to be sensitive to thermal cycling. Composite samples taken from the center of the panels were observed under the scanning electron microscope.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 AU Signals and Mechanical Properties

Figure 3 illustrates typical AU signals in the time and frequency domains for the composite, unexposed and after 40 thermal exposures (AU measurements taken perpendicular to the fibre direction). The shape of the signals was complex and distinct for the composite and the resin. In this example, there is a transformation in the AU signal amplitude in both the time and frequency domains for exposed specimens. However, it was more difficult to pick out variations by eye for resin and composite specimens that had been exposed to lower number of thermal cycles. It is for those cases that signal processing analysis was especially helpful.

Figure 3. AU signals and corresponding frequency spectra for the composite, measurements \perp to the fibres: a) Unexposed specimen b) exposed to 40 thermal cycles

Features that were best in classifying the signals according to the state of degradation of the material were selected for the neat resin, for the composite with AU measurements taken parallel to the fibres and for the composite with AU measurements perpendicular to the fibres. To simplify the problem, only three out of the five steps of the thermal cycling were considered: virgin, 11 and 21 cycles of thermal exposure for the resin and, virgin, 20 and 40 cycles for the composite. Although the feature vectors were not exactly the same for the resin and composite (parallel and perpendicular to the fibres), some features were common.

As the signal energy was one of the signal parameters most affected by changes in the material due to thermal cycling, the change in the signal energy as an example was chosen for comparison with the change in mechanical properties. Figure 4 shows the normalized values of the AU signal energy along with normalized values of the strength obtained for the resin and the composite.

In the case of the resin, the tensile strength did not change significantly after exposure to thermal cycling; variations were within the standard deviation. However, the AU signal energy decreased by about 27% after the first five cycles of thermal cycling; i.e. the variation was greater than the

standard deviation. This suggests that the thermal cycles were not severe enough to degrade the material to the extent that would affect the strength, but minute changes in the microstructure and morphology of the matrix may have been responsible for the changes in stress wave propagation efficiency that were observed.

Figure 4. AU signal energy and strength: a) for the resin b) for the composite

In the case of the composite, it appears that the interface properties may have been slightly degraded as shown by the shear strength in Figure 4b. The AU signal energy decreased with thermal cycling but it was much more pronounced in the case of the energy obtained in the direction perpendicular to the fibres (60% after 40 cycles) than in the direction parallel to the fibres (20% after 40 cycles). This reduction could be expected as AU measurements perpendicular to the fibres are related more to the matrix than measurements in the fibre direction and a reduction had been observed in the neat resin. The fibre/matrix interface may have also contributed to the reduction in energy as the decrease in the direction perpendicular to the fibres was greater than that observed in the neat resin.

4.2 Signal Classification

The ten original AU signals coming from each panel (3) of a same material (either the resin, the composite with AU measurements taken parallel to the fibres or the composite with AU measurements perpendicular to the fibres) which experienced the same conditioning were gathered together to form datasets with a total of 30 signals. Each dataset was subdivided: one half composed of 15 signals for each step of degradation (for example, for the composite with measurements parallel to the fibres, 15 signals for virgin, 15 signals for 20 times of exposure and 15 signals for 40 times of exposure). This training set was used to generate the decision rule which was then applied to the other half of the dataset to test them for classification procedure based on linear discriminant analysis. From the training set, the coefficients required to classify the signals are computed. The coefficients are then applied to the same data set in a process called cross-validation which is an important step in assessing the performance of the classification. Table 2a gives the results of the cross validation of the training signals from the resin samples. It can be seen that misclassification rate is about 9% (total of 6 out of 45 misclassified) indicating thus the successful clustering procedure using only 8 features. The results from the testing step given in Table 2b show that 14 out of 15 signals are recognized from virgin samples, 11 out of 15 signals belong to 11 times exposure cluster and finally 14 out of 15 signals are classified in the 21 times exposure cluster. In the case of unidirectional composite where the AU measurements were taken perpendicular to the fibres (Table 3) the recognition rate was 96%. This rate increased to 100% when only the signals from virgin specimens and

specimens exposed to 40 cycles were used. However, the recognition rate decreased to 78% for the signals from the AU measurements taken parallel to the fibres (with 0, 20 and 40 cycles of exposure).

Table 2. Cross-validation and classification for the resin

	Number of observations and % classified as			
	virgin	11 cycles	21 cycles	Total
virgin	14 93.33	1 6.67	0 0	15 100
11 cycles	2 13.33	12 80	1 6.67	15 100
21 cycles	0 0	0 0	15 100	15 100
Total	16	13	16	45
Percent	35.56	28.89	35.56	100
Error count estimate				
Rate	0.0667	0.2	0	0.0889

a) Cross-validation

	Number of observations and % classified as			
	virgin	11 cycles	21 cycles	Total
virgin	14 93.33	1 6.67	0 0	15 100
11 cycles	4 26.67	11 73.33	0 0	15 100
21 cycles	0 0	1 6.67	14 93.33	15 100
Total	18	13	14	45
Percent	40	28.89	31.11	100

b) Classification

Table 3. Classification for the composite with AU measurements \perp to the fibres

	Number of observations and % classified as			
	virgin	20 cycles	40 cycles	Total
virgin	13 86.67	2 13.33	0 0	15 100
20 cycles	0 100	15 100	0 100	15 100
40 cycles	0 0	0 0	15 100	15 100
Total	13	17	15	45
Percent	28.89	37.78	33.33	100

The preliminary results obtained using the neural network showed that the technique has some potential in detecting thermal degradation in composites. The neural network was trained to recognize and separate AU signals from virgin composite panels (AU measurements perpendicular to the fibres) from those obtained after 30 times of exposure. Out of 30 signals in the testing dataset, only 4 signals were badly classified, which is comparable to the results obtained with the statistical multivariate analysis.

4.3 C-Scan and Microscopic Observations

Visual examination of both the resin and the composite panels revealed the presence of degradation (darkening in the case of the resin and delamination in the composite) around the edges of the panels but no change could be seen in the center. Obviously, the temperature in the panels was not uniformly distributed. However, AU measurements were taken from the center of the panels where temperature was measured and mechanical testing was performed on specimens also cut from the center of the panel. The C-Scans did not indicate any degradation at the center of composite panels, again only at the edges of the panel. The SEM examination of composite samples taken from the center of the panel revealed that there were some signs of thermal degradation of exposed specimens (matrix debonding) and this was more evident as the number of thermal cycles increased.

5. CONCLUSION

The acousto-ultrasonic technique along with advanced pattern recognition analysis can be used for monitoring progressive degradation in neat resins and composites and for assessing variations in mechanical strength due to overheating. The thermal degradation observed from the microscopic observations appeared to have a greater effect on the stress wave propagation efficiency than on the mechanical properties rendering the AU technique potentially useful in the

early detection of thermal damage. However, further work is required to establish the applicability of these techniques to large and complex composite structures. Experimental measurements of AU signals on resin and composite panels and their classification using pattern recognition techniques indicated that it was possible to separate unexposed specimens from those which were exposed with good recognition rate. Further investigations are required to determine the powerfulness of the neural network pattern recognition technique to decipher AU signals according to the state of degradation of the material.

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